

Date: 23.11. 2021

PRESS RELEASE

Joint Communication StandICT.eu 2023 & SPATIAL

Two European Initiatives Join Forces to Foster Standards for AI in Cybersecurity

Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) signed between SPATIAL & StandICT.eu 2023

PISA – Italy, 23.11. 2021 - StandICT.eu 2023 & SPATIAL kick-off their collaboration to reinforce standardization procedures for AI in cybersecurity.

StandICT.eu 2023 is a European initiative supporting the EU engagement in international ICT standardization. It has two key axes; firstly, it will fund **400+ European fellowships in ICT standardisation** in a series of 10 Open calls providing a total of 3M€ of funding. Secondly, it operates the **European Observatory for ICT Standardisation (EUOS)** that is an interactive online ecosystem including an up-to-date standards repository as well as working groups sharing insights about ongoing standardization efforts across different initiatives. StandICT.eu 2023 focuses on horizontal and vertical ICT fields as defined in the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation¹, among the focus areas are **Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Cybersecurity**.

The EU funded **SPATIAL** project is working towards a **trustworthy governance and regulatory framework for AI-driven security** in Europe. It aims at societal impact by creating practical **guidelines on regulation, governance, and standardisation procedures** for AI in cybersecurity. The MoU can consolidate even further this commitment.

*To foster the uptake of AI tools in cybersecurity among different end-users, and especially our European SMEs, it is necessary to process fresh and informed standards for AI in cybersecurity. Therefore, this cross-project effort gathering European experts is a great momentum to drive dedicated recommendations and actual contributions that reinforce the EU positioning in this field. And we are delighted to welcome the SPATIAL partners in the StandICT.eu 2023 experts' community making the EU engagement more visible and concrete on the international standardisation scene. – says **Mona Marill, Project Manager at AUSTRALO Marketing Lab, a partner in the StandICT.eu 2023 Team.***

¹https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/european-standards/ict-standardisation_en

The StandICT.eu 2023 project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - Research and Innovation programme - under grant agreement no. 951972. SPATIAL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808. The content of this website does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

*My main expectation in SPATIAL is to effectively enhance trustworthy AI deployment and data governance in cybersecurity. This expectation is both ambitious and pragmatic, given the strong consortium of SPATIAL and a high demand by the EU to safeguard upcoming AI-driven safety and security services. We are very pleased to join forces with StandICT.eu 2023, as we see standards as a key enabler to make our vision for the SPATIAL project effective – says [Aaron Ding](#), **SPATIAL Project Coordinator at TU DELFT, the Netherlands**.*

In June 2021, StandICT.eu 2023 Technical Work Group (TWG) on AI published a [landscape report](#) providing an overview of the diverse array of global standardisation work underway in Artificial Intelligence and the various organisations behind it. In addition, the StandICT.eu 2023 TWG CYBER is working on a similar report published in the field of cybersecurity, and SPATIAL partners are invited to bring their expertise in this work.

SPATIAL kicked-off their activities last September and will be live for three years. Among their activities [four different pilots will be executed to demonstrate concrete use cases concerning AI in ICT systems and cybersecurity](#). They will cover a broad range of use cases, including elements on privacy, network security, cybersecurity and even eCall emergency systems. The participation of major players of the industry and recognised research centers, envision a solid impact for the technology SPATIAL will develop.

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For more information & contact of **StandICT.eu**

StandICT.eu 2023 runs from the 1st of September 2020 for a period of 36 months. The Consortium of Partners includes Trust-IT SRL (Coordinator) (Italy), Dublin City University (Ireland) and AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab SL (Spain). This CSA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - Research and Innovation programme - under the grant agreement no. 951972.

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For more information & contact of **SPATIAL**

SPATIAL runs from the 1st of September 2021 for a period of 36 months. The consortium is coordinated by Technische Universiteit Delft (Netherlands) and it includes 12 partners from 8 countries. This RIA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 - Research and Innovation programme - under grant agreement No. 101021808

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